

SPECIFIC ASPECTS AND PROBLEMS IN INDIA'S MULTI-VECTOR GEOPOLITICS

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Abstract

This article is devoted to the analysis of India's multi-vector foreign policy, its main aspects and the main problems facing the country in the context of changing global geopolitical processes. It mainly discusses directions and problematic situations in India's relations with the USA, Russia and China.

Keywords: global power centers, strategic cooperation, coalitions, Indo-Pacific region, BRICS, SCO

Introduction

According to Indian experts, "the world is moving in the direction of multipolarity, which may turn into a U.S.-China bipolar system for a long time." Delhi, for its part, is trying to guard against China's claims of global dominance. At the same time, India's current government has ambitious, long-term goals to strengthen its international reputation as a "serious global power" while creating new opportunities to accelerate its development and economic growth. According to experts, India can attain the status of a great power only if it succeeds in "creating multilateral organizations that independently protect its interests and express its values."

Main part

India is currently trying to balance its growing strategic partnership with the United States by strengthening and diversifying ties with Russia and establishing a comprehensive partnership with China.

The developments currently taking place in greater Asia and the Asia-Pacific region (what Americans and many others call the Indo-Pacific region) appear to be in India's interests. Almost all the countries interested in this huge area, which is gradually becoming one of the main regions of the world, are seeking to cooperate closely with Delhi in order to achieve both their tactical and long-term strategic goals. This means that the full implementation of Washington's Indo-Pacific project and Beijing's concept of "Community of Shared Destiny" can be realized with India's integral participation. Without India's participation, the Chinese project may not be completed and may continue only in continental status. The same is the case with the US Indo-Pacific strategy.

However, it should be noted that both of these initiatives impose a supporting role on Delhi. India is also seeking to enhance its role as a South Asian "system builder" while trying to maintain maximum freedom of maneuver and flexibility in international relations.

Thus, the geopolitical aspect of relations between India, China and the US is becoming increasingly complex and multifaceted. On the one hand, Beijing and Delhi recognize the objective need to restore the walls, China is interested in strengthening cooperation with

India, especially in the context of the current confrontation with Washington. On the other hand, the structural factors that hinder the qualitative improvement of Sino-Indian relations remain very relevant. These are manifested, first of all, in the struggle for spheres of influence in Asia and the persistence of a large difference in growing economic indicators. Therefore, Delhi is taking steps to prevent China's influence from spreading over a wide area from the Indian Ocean to the Pacific Ocean. Delhi would first gain some leverage against China by strengthening ties with the United States, Japan, and Australia as part of a hypothetical "Asian Entente." India is also counting on Shiite Iran to offset Beijing's growing influence in Sunni Pakistan, India's "main historical rival".

As for the US, it is playing a very important partner for India, primarily as a counterbalance to China. Washington, for its part, considers India a "vital and necessary partner" in protecting its interests in the entire Indo-Pacific region. At the same time, Washington's long-term political goals are multifaceted: a) to limit China's growing influence throughout Greater Asia, including Pakistan; b) preventing a military-political alliance between China, Pakistan and Iran; c) strengthen relations with India by working primarily through Pakistan and Afghanistan. Meanwhile, any escalation of tensions between Delhi and Islamabad could further strain relations between India and China. American political observers analyze that this situation does not correspond to the main interests of the two major countries, which are considered "doomed" to remain strategic rivals in the entire Indian Ocean region. Therefore, there is a high probability that the two giants of Asia will remain in the "middle" position for many years. As some experts put it, "they are torn between not being ready to give up and not being able to move forward."

The relatively slow pace of socio-economic development remains the main obstacle to strengthening India's position in Asia and other countries of the world. India is suffering from "standard growing problems" that usually accompany accelerated changes in the economy and society. Social inequality is increasing, corruption is widespread, the country lacks natural resources, and the environmental situation is deteriorating. These include repeated terrorist attacks, manifestations of separatism, and vestiges of traditionalism that constrain efforts to modernize Indian society. For this reason, intense discussions about the sustainability of the current models of socio-economic development in the country are increasing.

N.Modi's government, seeking to correct the growing imbalances in the country's development, is preparing and implementing large-scale reform programs in the economic, administrative and financial spheres. Officials are talking about increasing the national gross domestic product to 5 trillion dollars by 2024. At a time when the country's need for investment is increasing, the main goal is to attract both Chinese and US investors. Chinese money is not only giving a new impetus to India's economic development, but is also becoming a factor in mitigating existing contradictions.

Indian leaders had high hopes for the United States, but with a change of guard in the White House in early 2017, Washington began a policy of "bringing home" US investment and industrial capacity. Along with fundamental trends in the global capital markets, this has led to a significant decline in the interest of American investors to channel their money into projects in India. In addition, in June 2019, former President D. Trump declared an essentially trade war against India, stripping Delhi of trade privileges that would have prevented up to \$5.6 billion worth of Indian goods from being delivered duty-free to the US market. .

On December 1, 2018, the leaders of Russia, India and China met for the first time since 2006 within the framework of the G20 summit held in Argentina. At the meeting, Russia called on its partners to "closer coordination of the approaches of the three countries, primarily in the field of security and establishing constructive interstate relations in Eurasia." They also emphasized the partnership nature of relations between Beijing, Moscow and Delhi, and the compatibility of their interests and goals "in the field of development".

Moscow has been helping its Indian partners on a wide range of issues, from high technology and defense to modern infrastructure and poverty reduction. Delhi is interested in cooperation with Russia within BRICS and SCO. Before Prime Minister N. Modi's visit to the 5th Eastern Economic Forum in Vladivostok in September, Russian Deputy Prime Minister Yuri Trutnev and Indian Trade and Industry Minister Piyush Goyal discussed measures to increase the volume of mutual trade to 30 billion dollars by 2025. Also, the North-South International Transport Corridor is one of the long-term joint strategic projects for India and Russia.

At the second meeting within the framework of the G20 summit held in Japan in June 2019, the leaders of Russia, China and India praised the highly effective work being done in a single format to create an "equal and indivisible security architecture in Eurasia". However, India's reluctance to join China's Belt and Road Initiative shows the contradictions in India's foreign policy. On the one hand, India has reason to consider itself the country that will "ultimately determine which way the geo-economic pendulum swings" in almost the entire Eastern Hemisphere. On the other hand, it remains unclear to what extent India will be able to balance its interests between Greater Eurasia and Indo-Pacific projects.

Conclusion

Since India's independence in 1947, a multi-vector foreign policy has been a hallmark of the country's geopolitics. It is to this day that Delhi tries to stick to this line. The increasing uncertainty in the existing international system is one of the objective trends of the last few decades, and India remains one of the many countries that participate in several rival coalitions at the same time, although the real nature of these coalitions goals often conflict with each other.

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